

Cataract surgery and capsular pseudoexfoliation about 33 cases

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Abstract: Summary: Background: Capsular pseudoexfoliation syndrome [CPS] is a provider of complications during cataract surgery, following a poor expansion of iris and zonular desinsertion Methodology: we conducted a retrospective study of 33 cases of CPS 364 patients scheduled for cataract surgery in the ophthalmology department of the military hospital over a period of 1 year. Results: We have found 9% prevalence, frequent in the male sex, often associated with glaucoma with open angle, a poor expansion of iris, complications per operative are greater in patients with capsular pseudoexfoliation. The CPS is a common condition among patients scheduled for cataract surgery with a prevalence of 9.74%, affecting the elderly, the majority of studies reported a highly significant association with primary open angle glaucoma, and exposes more to intraoperative complications, during cataract surgery, related to poor dilation and postoperative, in particular corneal decompensations. Conclusion: The CPS should always be sought in patients who are candidates for cataract surgery, especially if they are elderly, finally, we insist on the usefulness of a large-scale multicentric and randomized and multifactorial work devoted to the study of the CPS.

Keywords: Capsular pseudoexfoliation syndrome, cataracts, glaucoma

INTRODUCTION:

Capsular pseudoexfoliation syndrome (CPS) has been known since 1917 according to the work carried out by a young ophthalmologist Lindberg [1, 2];

Its exact etiopathogenesis still remains unknown. It is defined as an age-related generalized systemic degenerative fibrillopathy, and is characterized by the production and abnormal deposition of

pseudoexfoliative fibrillary material in several viscera: liver, lung, heart, kidneys, and the eye especially the anterior segment.

The diagnosis of exfoliative syndrome is clinically easy in its complete form by whitish deposits on the anterior aspect of the lens forming a pathognomonic cockade image and localized iris atrophy.

The prevalence is variable, ranging from 0% in Eskimos and at altitudes above 4000 meters, 2-18% in Western Europe, the United States or Japan, 5.5% in France [3], 16% among Australian aborigines and 38% among Navajo Indians [4].

In Scandinavia, the prevalence is high, 10 to 43% for patients over 60 years [5]. In Morocco, the prevalence in a candidate population for cataract surgery was 9.8% [6]. In addition, the prevalence increases with age with 1% of patients with CEP are under 60 years old, and 10% are over 80 years old [3].

Among patients with CPS, 25% develop ocular hypertonia or chronic open-angle glaucoma [7,8].

The PEC causes changes in all ocular tissues with the risk of spontaneous complications: poor dilation,

fragility zonulaire, phacododésis, subluxation cristallinienne, breaking the barrier hématoaqueuse, endothelial damage, desinsertion zonulaire intraoperative, décompensation corneo-endothéliale, postoperative inflammation, hypertension postoperative, subluxation of the posterior chamber implant, secondary cataract [3,9].

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

We conducted a retrospective study of 33 cases of CPS in 364 patients scheduled for cataract surgery. These patients were collected over a period of 1 year.

RESULTS:

364 patients operated on for cataract, CPS is reported in 33 cases, so prevalence of 9%.

The average age is 69 years, with the prevalence of CPS increasing proportionately with age.

Male about 66% against 33% of sex female (sex ratio of 2 men for 1 woman).

The involvement was bilateral in about half of the cases.

There is a frequent association between CPS and chronic glaucoma.

The corticosteroid nuclear cataract represents the predominant type followed by white cataract in 40% of cases.

Nine patients were noted cases of poor expansion.

The surgical techniques used are: phacoemulsification (PKE) in 30 patients, manual extracapsular extraction (EEC) in 3 patients with placement of an intraocular implant in the posterior chamber of the 30 eyes operated by phacoemulsification, there was one case of minimal zonular desinsertion and no case of capsular rupture.

DISCUSSION:

CPS is currently defined as an age-related condition whose prevalence increases significantly beyond the age of 60.

The studies carried out, in the world, concerning the CPS show great variations according to the countries, thus in South Africa the prevalence is estimated between 6% and 7.7% [10], in Tunisia it is at 11% [11], and in Ethiopia the prevalence is 39.3% [12], Arnarssona [13] in 2009 on a large sample found a prevalence of 10.7% and in

Morocco, Tahri et al [6] in 2006 reported a biased prevalence of 9.8% almost similar to that calculated in our series which is 9% but does not reflect the true prevalence of CPS because it is a study on a non-randomized population since it is based on a group of patients scheduled and selected for cataract surgery, In our study, the mean age of patients was 69 years in the CPS group.

The prevalence increases with age [5] would be around 58% in a population over 65 years against 30% in the study by Ritch [14]. In our series we note a predominance of the male sex at 66% against 33% of the female sex; Several studies have found similar results [15].

On the other hand, women are more affected in the Scandinavian countries and in Australia [16]. In our study, half of the cases of CPS are bilateral; According to the study by Puska [17], it is a bilateral involvement, but asymmetric presentation with a long delay between the two eyes with an evolution towards bilateralization at 10 years in 38% of cases; In unilateral forms, the eye with clinical PEC presents with poorer visual acuity, higher IOP, less dilation, greater cataract, and more pigmented trabeculum [18]. Secondary

chronic open-angle glaucoma (GCAO) is present in approximately 40 to 60% of PEC patients [19]. In unilateral CPS, glaucoma occurs on the side where CPS is manifest [20]. Conversely, among the glaucomatous, 10-8 5% present a CPS[5, 21] ; this is explained by the fact that the increase in resistance to the flow of aqueous humor, associated with the increase in its viscosity, is at the origin of a predisposition to the development of glaucoma in patients with a syndrome Pseudoexfoliation ;. The cortico-nuclear cataract represents the predominant type followed by the white cataract, these results partially agree with the data of the literature which finds a greater frequency of nuclear cataracts [18]; this is probably due to the delay in consulting patients or the treatment is only at a very advanced stage.

In our series, poor iris dilation is linked to CPS, which joins the majority of studies [24, 3] and, of course, exposes to intraoperative difficulties .

CPS as a risk factor for cataract surgery is a subject of controversy, with some studies showing a difference and others not between the CPS and control groups [26, 5].

The results are a function of the surgeon's experience and good dilation, in our study the rate of intraoperative complications was minimal, nevertheless an edematous decompensation of the cornea was objectified in patients with CPS.

CONCLUSION:

The CPS is recognized news actually as a affection multisystem and which should be sought systématiquement to ophthalmological examination especially in patients scheduled for anterior segment surgery, we must systematically seek an intraocular hypertension or chronic open-angle glaucoma and without failing to request a cardiovascular examination In this retrospective study, we compared the clinical and epidemiological characteristics of 74 patients with CPS to another group of 686 patients without CPS, all operated for cataracts. The prevalence of CPS was 9.74%, with no particular laterality. CPS is significantly associated with chronic open-angle glaucoma, poor iris dilation, low pre- and postoperative visual acuity and postoperative corneal edema; moreover intraoperative complications are the same in both groups.

REFERENCES :

- 1-Guo S, Gewirtz M, Thaker R, Reed M.Characterizing pseudoexfoliation syndrome through the use of ultrasound biomicroscopy. JCatract Refract Surg, 2006;32:614
- 2-Tarkkanen A., Kivelä T John G. Lindberg and the discovery of exfoliation syndrome. Acta Ophthalmol Scand 2002 ; 80:151-4.
- 3- Strehlo M, Rohart C, Chaîne G Le syndrome de pseudo-exfoliation capsulaire dans la chirurgie de la cataracte. Étude rétrospective de 37 cas J Fr. Ophtalmol., 2008; 31, 1, 11-15 J Fr. Ophtalmol., 2008 ; 31, 1, 11-15
- 4- Faulkner HW. Pseudoexfoliation of the lens among the Navajo Indians. Am J Ophthalmol 1971 ; 72 : 206-207
- 5-Kling F, Colin J, Syndrome pseudoexfoliatif, Encyclopédie Médico-Chirurgicale 21-250-A-40
- 6- Benatiya Andaloussi I, Tahri H et coll. Le syndrome pseudo-exfoliatif Chez les patients marocains Programmes pour chirurgie de La cataracte, Bull. Soc. belge Ophtalmol., 300, 57-64, 2006.
- 7-Arvind H, Raju P, Paul P.G et coll Pseudoexfoliation in South India. Br J Ophthalmol. 2003 ; 87:1321-3.
- 8-Krishnadas R, Nirmalan P.K et coll Pseudoexfoliation in a rural population of southern India: the Aravind Comprehensive Eye Survey. Am J Ophthalmol. 2003;135:830-7.
- 9- Naumann GO, Schlotzer-Schrehardt U, Kuchle M. Pseudoexfoliation syndrome for the comprehensive ophthalmologist. Intraocular and systemic manifestations. Ophthalmology, 1998 ;105:951-68.
- 10- Rotchford A.P, Kirwan J.F, et coll, Exfoliation syndrome in black South Africans. Arch Ophthalmol. 2003 ;121:863-70.
- 11- Ayed S, Ghorbel M, Nacef L. The exfoliation syndrome in Tunisia. Tunis Med 1990 ; 68: 19-22.
- 12- Teshome T, Regassa K. Prevalence of pseudoexfoliation syndrome in Ethiopian patients scheduled for cataract surgery. Acta Ophthalmol Scand. 2004; 82:254-8.
- 13- Arnarssona A, Karim F, Damjic et coll, Pseudoexfoliation in the Reykjavik Eye Study: Five-Year Incidence and Changes in Related Ophthalmologic Variables American Journal of Ophthalmology Volume 148, Issue 2, August 2009, Pages 291-297
- 14- Ritch R, Schlotzer-Schrehardt U. Exfoliation syndrome. Surv Ophthalmol, 2001; 45: 265-315.
- 15-Aasved H. The geographical distribution of fibrillographia epitheliocapsularis, so-called senile exfoliation or pseudoexfoliation of the anterior lens capsule. Acta Ophthalmol 1969 ; 47 : 792-810

16-Buhrmann R, Quigley H et Coll, Prevalence of glaucoma in a rural East African population. Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci 2000; 41: 40-48.

17- Puska PM. Unilateral exfoliation syndrome: conversion to bilateral exfoliation and to glaucoma: a prospective 10-year follow-up study. J Glaucoma, 2002;11: 517-24.

18- Schlotzer-Schrehardt U, Naumann GO. Ocular and systemic pseudoexfoliation syndrome. Am J Ophthalmol, 2006 ; 141:921-37.

19-Forsius H. Exfoliation syndrome in various ethnic populations. Acta Ophthalmol [suppl] 1988 ; 184 : 71-85

20-Roth M, Epstein L. Exfoliation syndrome. Am J Ophthalmol 1980 ; 89 : 477- 481

21-Kling F. Contribution à l'analyse actuelle du syndrome pseudo-exfoliatif (PEC). [thèse], Université de Bretagne Occidentale, 1999

22-Shingleton Bradford J, Crandall Alan S. Pseudoexfoliation and the cataract surgeon, Journal of cataract and refractive surgery , 2009, vol. 35, no6, pp. 1101-1120

23- Merkur A, Damji KF, Mintsioulis G, Hodge WG. Intraocular pressure decrease after phacoemulsification in patients with pseudoexfoliation syndrome. J Cataract Refract Surg, 2001 ; 27:528-32.

24- Damji KF, Konstas AG, Liebmann JM et coll, Intraocular pressure following phacoémulsification in patients with and

without exfoliation syndrome: a 2 year prospective study. Br J Ophthalmol, 2006 ; 90:1014-8.

25-Shastri L, Vasavada A. Phacoemulsification in Indian eyes with pseudoexfoliationsyndrome. J Cataract Refract Surg. 2001; 27:1629-37.

26- Hyams M, Mathalone N, Herskovitz M et coll, Intraoperative complications of phacoemulsification in eyes with and without pseudoexfoliation. J Cataract Refract Surg, 2005 ; 31:1002-5.